

**IMPACT OF TANNERY WASTE ON SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL BALANCE
AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF BANGLADESH**

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Abstract:

The research is performed to evaluate the consciousness of peoples on the impact of tannery waste disposal on social- ecological-health sector of some sorted out areas in Bangladesh. Data were collected by interviewing 350 peoples randomly of which 115 were labor, 75 livestock farmers, 68 fishermen, 38 students, 35 housewife and 19 were in local people in the research areas. Data were collected on age, education level, disease type, environmental effect, human diseases, environmental pollution awareness, preventive measures livestock diseases, livestock production and fisheries production. The research show that maximum of the respondents had low environmental pollution awareness because of their ignorance. Education, occupation and type of disease had significant positive relationship where literacy, age, gender have no relationship with their tannery waste pollution awareness. Identify the impact of tannery waste on various sector is the main objective of the research. The results of this research express that how tannery waste disposal affect the social ecological balance in Bangladesh.

Key Words: Social Ecology, Health Hazards, Tannery, Waste, Environment

Introduction:

Environmental pollution is one of the crucial troubles of the world and it is rising constantly because of urbanization and industrialization. The ongoing pattern of industrial movement change the natural flow of materials and introduces novel chemicals into the environment composed of water bodies, soil, plants, vegetables, human, and different living organism. Today water, air and soil pollution are the major issue of environment pollution. The contamination of water, air and soils with heavy metals initiates detrimental consequences not only on plants but also poses risks to human health, fertility, child development, social life, food habit, physical activity.

The research area are tanneries of Hazaribag of Dhaka and Mirsarai of Chattogram. Around 50,000 peoples are presently living in the slums in the study area, under awfully massively populated and insanitary conditions. The rivers of the tannery industry area are very much contaminated by the tannery wastes. As a result the livestock, plants, fish, cultivable land are significantly affected by the tannery waste disposal in these area.

The present research objective at inspecting the impacts of tannery waste disposal on water, soil and agricultural productivity of Bangladesh. In this research the author used descriptive research design. The author used statistical formula for data analysis purpose.

Thus the present research was initiated to attain the following objectives:

- To explore the present circumstances of the tannery industry surrounding environment in Bangladesh.
- To inspect the impact of tannery waste on social-ecological development of Bangladesh.
- To evaluate the environmental awareness and waste prevention measure of the population in tannery industry area of Bangladesh.

Literature Review:

Ecology is the study of the relationships between living organisms, including humans, and their physical environment; it seeks to understand the vital connections between plants and animals and the world around them. Social ecology is the study of how individuals interact with and respond to the environment around them, and how these interactions affect society and the environment as a whole.

Founded by activist Murray Bookchin, social ecology is an approach to society that embraces an ecological, reconstructive, and communitarian view on society. This ideology looks to reconstruct and transform current outlooks on both social issues and environmental factors while promoting direct democracy.

Bangladesh tannery industry is well established and ranked second in terms of export earnings. Because of its high value addition, huge growth and employment opportunities, leather sector has already been declared a top priority sector. Bangladesh accounts for 3% share in the global leather and products market.

Tannery industry discharge untreated effluent which has a strong potential harm impact on soil and water. Tannery waste is the primary pollutant of the environment. Tannery industry of Bangladesh uses more than 250 chemicals for leather goods production and emit a complex mixture of toxic organic chemicals like toxic organic chlorinated phenols, azo-dyes, arsenic and other toxic pollutants such as zinc, mercury, selenium, lead, resins. This toxic pollutants released by every tannery industry which cause adverse impact on health, fertility on human and other living beings.

Environment Pollution Issue:

In Bangladesh the largest tannery industry is Savar tannery zone, the rest of the two tannery industry is situated in Rajshahi and the other in the Mirsarai area of Chattogram. These tannery industry released 40 thousand cubic meters of liquid waste per day. Proper solid waste management has not been established in these area.

Tannery waste contains large amounts of pollutants, such as salt, lime sludge, sulfides, and acids. The process of tanning stabilizes the collagen or protein fibers in skins so that they actually stop biodegrading-otherwise, the leather would rot right in our closet.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Social Ecological Balance in Bangladesh:

The people who live in the tannery industry are severely affected by the pollution cause by tannery effluent. Fishing is one of the main occupations of Bangladesh. Thousand of fisher men live in the tannery industry area in Bangladesh. Those fishermen earned a living by catching fish in a five-kilometre stretch of the Dhaleshwari River from Fulbaria to Vakurta downstream. But the Savar tannery industrial estate dumping their waste into the Dhaleshwari River, as a result the river water is polluted, fishes are not alive and most of the fisher men gradually leave their profession because they are not getting any fish in the river.

The Dhaleshwari river water is heavily polluted day by day. As a result various diseases spread out because of using the polluted water. The inhabitants can't sleep well due to a sickening stench. If the inhabitants used the water for farming or washing livestock they are severally affected or died. Their children and women are affected by various water borne diseases. The Dhaleshwari river is the lifeline of the areas. From daily household chores to fishing, farming, bathing, transporting almost everything of their life revolved around the Dhaleshwari River.

This river is the main source of water for all the living beings on the bank of the river. According to the chairman of Hazratpur union of Bangladesh, the tannery effluent hampered life to over three lac people in this area.

Health Hazards:

Tannery waste emit various type of solid metals that affect human health directly. Tanneries waste have a significant effects on health, many diseases such as dizziness, headache, irritation of eyes, skin or lungs, allergic reactions, poisoning of liver, kidney are arise due to tannery waste. Tannery work involves exposure to chromium, solvents, and other chemicals, which has been associated with adverse pregnancy and fertility outcomes in animals or humans in some studies. Though tannery industry is one of the biggest industries of Bangladesh which has a huge impact on our economy, large amount of tannery wastes dump into the rivers as well as land that have made an inhabitable situation for the living people of those areas. Poisonous chemical and other toxic waste products of the tannery industry create air, odor, water, and soil pollution, etc. which all severely impact living conditions.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Plant Growth & Plant Life:

Tannery waste cause water pollution, this polluted water affects plant growth and the accumulation of toxic heavy metals are bio magnified at various trophic levels through food chain. Tannery waste water produce heavy metals which cause stress for plants. The high conglomeration of heavy metals have a severe impact on various metabolic process of plants which cause reduction of vegetative and at the end on reproductive growth of the plants and trees.

Water Profiles:

Tannery waste are largely affect the water because they color and diminish the quality of water bodies into which they are released. The tannery effluent impact mainly on the loss of dissolved oxygen. Which is very deleterious to aquatic organisms and stimulate anaerobic activity that accelerate release of noxious gases. This gases destroy water plants.

Atmospheric Systems:

Tannery waste has a severe impact on the atmospheric system. The tannery waste emit heavy metals, sulphur dioxide, benzene, carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, H₂S and NH₃ which contaminate the air. Various type of waste discharging from tanning during unheating limning and delimiting bating process cause air pollution.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Poultry:

Bangladesh is a heavily populated developing country where poultry is one of the prime inexpensive sources of protein as human diet. Some farms reared poultry using feed made from tannery solid waste. Now chromium was detected in the collected poultry feeds in Bangladesh. The chromium content was found to be accumulated in the body parts of chickens reared with the chrome-containing poultry feed. Finding out amounts of chromium (III) is essential for certain metabolic functions in the human body. But, excessive heavy metals may cause serious disease of human.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Cattle:

In Tannery industry area the health of the cattle adversely affects by the toxic pollutants of tanneries. Cattle and livestock are attack by various diseases such as hepatitis, cancer, gastrointestinal diseases, mastitis and skin diseases. These diseases are spreading rapidly in domestic animals on account of polluted air and water of tanneries. The reproduction and growth of domestic animals are harmfully affected owing to these pollutants. Consequently these pollutants affects milk and meat production of cattle. People who take or consume these contaminated milk and meat may affected by various diseases.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Food Chain:

Tannery waste emits various metal pollutants which are potentially toxic elements. These toxic metals certainly detrimental for human health when transported via the food chain. The toxicological effects of chromium on the human health consumed through different food items. Tannery industry produced solid waste, these waste mainly consist of skin trimmings, keratin wastes, fleshing wastes, chrome shaving wastes, and buffing wastes .Report show that chrome shaving dusts, wet blue scraps, and buffing dusts contain huge amount of chromium. Research showed that chrome shaving dusts contain chromium in the range of 10.68 ± 1.98 mg/g .Through away of this high chromium content solid wastes as land fill or dumping these may cause leaching of chromium to groundwater and thus cause its entry into the human food chain.

Weak Waste Management Facilities:

The deficiency of proper waste management in tanneries in Bangladesh one of the main root of environmental pollution. Besides tannery industries of Bangladesh have a great lack of qualified and skilled manpower. Because of improper skills, tannery workers take longer working hours and do not secure proper quality. Consequently, the product rejection count also enhance notably, which is a big challenge for this sector. Apart from, the environment in and around tannery industry area is very dirty due to poor waste management. Furthermore, most tanneries do not follow basic health compliance guidelines, which poses a major health and safety problem for all living beings in these area.

Impact of Tannery Waste on Social-Economic Development of BD:

Tannery waste pollution not only affects the health of our communities, living creatures and ecosystems, it also has a real and very significant economic impact. This includes lower land values, reduced tourism, wasted resources and clean-up costs. For a long time river pollution and fresh water depletion due to the increase of tannery industry in Bangladesh are causing severe health and economic problem. So the increasing number of tannery industry in Bangladesh pulled the economy of the country and hampered the ecosystem. Ultimately the environmental pollution is unacceptable. Though the export earnings from the tannery industry is very positive but tanneries effluents are responsible for ill health and ecological depletion. The tannery effluent diminishes the quality of the river water extremely. This hinder the continue economic growth of any country. The rapid industrialization of tannery causes heavy losses to economic welfare in terms of health and ecological balance. Again tannery effluent cause various livestock diseases and reduce fertility and production of livestock. Besides tannery effluent affects fisheries along with by decreasing its production rapidly.

Preventive Measures Against Tannery Waste:

Tannery has one of the greatest impacts on eutrophication of all materials used for fashion, a serious ecological problem in which runoff waste creates an overgrowth of plant life in water systems, which suffocates animals by depleting oxygen levels in the water and is the leading cause of hypoxic zones. Use of different chemicals during leather processing produces wastes in solid, liquid and gaseous form. Exposure to different chemicals is the main cause of soil pollution, atmospheric pollution, water pollution and air pollution. Introduction: Leather industry is one of the most polluting industries. Tannery production not only requires a significant amount of water, but it also pollutes natural waterways. Polluted water dumped out of tanneries and slaughterhouses and which runs off farms and feedlots, can lead to environmental pollution and eutrophication. Some examples of cleaner production methods that can be adopted in leather production include: Low-impact tanning: Low-impact tanning methods, such as vegetable or chrome-free tanning, use less water and fewer hazardous chemicals, resulting in lower levels of waste and pollution.

Case Study 1: Agriculture

The waste of the tannery industry have embarrassed the farmers of Fulbaria Savar and its nearby areas. The soil is unable to represent rich fertility. One of the respondents very pessimistically shares his ideas about his agricultural land as: "I have 12 acres of agricultural land but only 5 acres are able for cultivation and the remaining 7 acres is fall prey to erosion due to mixing toxic effluents of tanneries in the groundwater of the surrounding area.

Case Study 2: Fertility

Reproductive health is one of the rights for all both men and women where people of the tannery industry are exposed to hazardous chemicals by living in the tannery industry area for short or long time. One of the respondents very pessimistically shares about her not getting pregnancy as:"I have tried last three years to become pregnant but failed."

Table 1: Situation of pregnancy during living in the tannery industry area

Get pregnant during living in the tannery industry area	Number	Percent
Yes	34	26.98
No	92	73.02
Total	126	100

Table 1 show the situation of pregnancy during living in the tannery industry area that among the total female respondents 145 women were married and interestingly 19 were unmarried. In Table 4, only married women's information was given where Married women were asked whether they ever get pregnant during living in the tannery. About 26.98 % replied as yes whereas 73.02% replied as no that means they never get pregnant while living in the tannery area.

Case Study 3: Miscarriage

One of the respondents very pessimistically shares about her miscarriage as: "Coping with my miscarriage was traumatic. The medical staff contributed a lot to my grief despite the fact that I am a nurse too. The other issue is the cultural attitude. In most traditional Bangladeshi cultures, people think you can lose a baby because of a curse or witchcraft. Another woman shares about her miscarriage as, "I've had three miscarriages, all around 10 weeks gestation. I let them all happen naturally. I had a loving husband, a compassionate birthing team and I felt spiritually grounded about them. And even in the best of circumstances, I was devastated every single time."

Significance of Tannery Industry on the Economic Development of BD:

In Bangladesh the tannery produced goods industry is a prime sector of export earnings. Tannery products are considered the second largest foreign exchange earner of Bangladesh. In Bangladesh the tannery sector employs around 600,000 people directly and another 300,000 people indirectly. Tannery sector contributes four percent of total export of Bangladesh. Tannery industry own 0.5% of the total GDP of Bangladesh. Although the tannery waste have a severe impact on our environment and ecological balance but its economic benefits is undeniable.

Relating the research with SDG:

This research topic is harmonized with three sustainable development goals such as,

- SDG 6 - Clean Water and Sanitation.
- SDG 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production.
- SDG 13 - Climate Action.

The aim of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are to transform our world. This research focused on the above mentioned three SDGs. Tannery waste affect clean water and sanitation and also influenced climate .This research also emphasis on the responsibility of consumption and production. This paper action to end poverty and inequality, protect the planet, and ensure that all people enjoy health, justice and prosperity in the tannery industry area of BD.

Research Design:

Here the author used descriptive research design. The researcher used descriptive research method because it is a common investigatory research model and descriptive research method used in various field like social science, biological science, linguistics etc. To conduct an effective research the author first study the scenario's or targeted population's who, what and where. In this research, "Who" indicate the 350 respondents of the tannery industry area in Bangladesh. The term "What" is the impact of tannery waste on the social ecological development of Bangladesh. And the term "Where" indicate the two tannery industry area of Bangladesh that is Dhaka and Chattogram. T his research main goal is to observe all the variables and situations that affect the phenomenon. Descriptive research is an exploratory research method. This research method enables the author to precisely and methodically describe the situation of the tannery industry area of Bangladesh. This exploratory research describe the attributes of the respondents, habitual behavior of the respondents ,natural feature of the tannery industry area being studied without manipulating variables or testing hypothesis.

This paper can be reported using surveys, observational studies and case studies. The researcher used both quantitative and qualitative methods to compile the data. Here the author making observations and then comparing and analyzing the data , this descriptive research design develop various relationship between living beings and the environment of the tannery industry area of Bangladesh, develop impact concept and provide solutions to critical issues. In this paper the descriptive research design used to answers how the event that is tannery waste disposal occurred, when the tannery waste disposal occurred and what the problem or impact of tannery waste disposal in Bangladesh. Here the author gathers quantifiable data to statistically analyze the population of the tannery industry area. These data showed patterns, connections, impact and trends over time of tannery waste disposal and can be discovered using surveys, polls and experiments.

This research is also qualitative. This qualitative part of the research gives meaning and context to the numbers supplied by the quantitative part of the paper. Here the author use tools like interviews, focus group and ethnographic studies to illustrate why tannery industry area people and other living beings are badly affected by the tannery waste disposal, and help characterize the research problem. This is because this research is more explanatory than exploratory or experimental research. It is a descriptive research so the researcher can not manipulate the variables such as health hazards, employment status,

food habit, social change. These variables are recognized, scrutinized and quantified instead. Which is one of the most prominent feature of the paper. It is a cross sectional studies also. Because this paper examine several areas of the same group that is tannery industry area inhabitants. This paper involves obtaining data on multiple variables at the personal level during a certain period of Bangladesh. This paper is helpful when trying to understand a larger community's change in terms of occupation, health, food habits, financial condition etc. This paper carried out in a natural environment. This descriptive research design usually carried the respondent's every day environment.

Research Methodology:

Here the researcher used statistical method to explaining and carryout her research. Here the author used a logical systematic plan to explain the research objectives. The method used by the author details the researcher's approach to the research to ensure reliable, valid results that address the objectives of the research. Here the author used both qualitative and quantitative method and mixed method of research. For data analysis purpose the author used some statistical method such as Person Correlation R test, independent t test and Chi-Square test. Health hazards, fertility, occupation, live stock, agriculture commodities are the variables of the research that have been identified by the authors for analyzing the social -ecological and economic risks. For that purpose a convenient sampling technique is used to collect data from the different tannery industry area of Bangladesh. A total of 350 respondents were interviewed .Here the author used a 1-5 Likert scale questionnaire for data collection purpose.

Here the author selected the respondents from different groups such as laborers, livestock farmers, fishermen, students, housewives, and local residents. Because different group peoples have different experience regarding tannery effluent. For research data collection the author faced some problems. Maximum of the laborers, farmers and housewives are illiterate or little learning as a consequences they could not respond correctly sometimes.

Data Analysis:

The population used in this study are people with a sample 350 respondents scattered across tannery industry area of Bangladesh (Dhaka & Chattogram). Samples were selected by intentional random sampling using a 1-5 Likert scale questionnaire. Research data analysis is performed by using Person Correlation R test, independent t test and Chi-Square test. Participants were then directed to questionnaire, where they completed a questionnaire about their experience with tannery waste that hampered social ecological balance in tannery industry area in Bangladesh. All questionnaires were self-administered. The testing process was completed when the participants finished their answers. The research method used is a quantitative descriptive method.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to their age

Age Group	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
Young (18-30)	86	24.57	38.52	10.82
Middle Age (31-50)	235	67.14		
Old (51-80)	29	8.29		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that middle age people are highest number of respondents in this area.

A standard deviation (or o) is a measure of how dispersed the data is in relation to the mean. Low, or small, standard deviation indicates data are clustered tightly around the mean, and high, or large, standard deviation indicates data are more spread out.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to their education level

Education Level	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
No Education	117	33.43	1.26	9.36
Primary Level	108	30.86		
Secondary Level	67	19.14		
Graduate Level	32	9.14		
Masters Level	26	7.43		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that no education or illiterate people are the highest number of respondents in these area, Higher education level people are very lower percentage. Standard deviation (SD) is a widely used measurement of variability used in statistics. It shows how much variation there is from the average (mean). A low SD indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean, whereas a high SD indicates that the data are spread out over a large range of values. The mean value is 1.26 indicate that most of the respondents are not agreed on that variable.The SD value is 9.36 indicates that there is a low stability of ideas on the specific variable.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents according to their Occupation

Occupation	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
Fisherman	68	19.43	2.87	8.37
Livestock Farmer	75	21.43		
Labor of tannery industry	115	32.86		
Student	38	10.86		

Housewife	35	10		
Others	19	5.43		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that tannery industry labor are the highest number of respondents in this research. The highest mean indicates that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. The lowest Standard deviation indicates that there is a stability of ideas on the specific variable. The mean value is 2.87 indicate that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. The SD value is 9.36 indicates that there is a low stability of ideas on the specific variable.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents according to effect of livestock sector

Effect of livestock sector	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
Fodder Toxicity	32	9.14	3.26	8.66
Movement problem	78	22.29		
Water problem	103	29.43		
Fertility problem	42	12		
Mortality	95	27.14		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that in the case of affected livestock sector water pollution and mortality is the highest number of problem. Here the mean is 3.26 indicate that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. Standard Deviation value is 8.66 which indicates there is a low stability of ideas on the specific variable.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to the effect of Health Issue

Health Issue	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
Dizziness, headache, irritation of eyes,	118	33.71	2.79	8.62
Miscarriage	56	16		
Poisoning of liver, kidney of human.	69	19.71		
Adverse pregnancy and fertility outcomes woman	67	19.14		
Skin or lungs, allergic reactions on human	40	11.43		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that the maximum number of respondents affected by Dizziness, headache, irritation of eyes. Miscarriage and adverse pregnancy and fertility outcomes rates of woman are in a serious level. The mean value is 2.79 which indicates that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. Standard Deviation value is 8.62 which indicate there is a low stability of ideas on the specific variable.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents according to effect of livestock's diseases

Livestock disease	Frequency of Respondent	% Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
Livestock/Poultry die	155	44.29	2.31	11.53
Livestock/Poultry skin disease	148	42.29		
Other disease	47	13.43		
Total	350	100		

The above table show that Livestock/Poultry die is the highest number of effects of tannery waste pollution. The mean value is 2.31 which indicates that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. Standard Deviation value is 11.43 which indicates there is a low stability of ideas on the specific variable.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents according to their awareness/preventive tool against tannery waste pollution

Taking Awareness/Preventive Method	Number of Respondent
Drawing the odorous air from the working atmosphere by exhaust fans and diluting with relatively clean air.	58
Removal of causative impurities from the tannery. Screening for removal of coarser impurities, hair and fleshing followed by settling for atleast 4 hours in a continuous flow settling tank form the essential primary treatment of tannery wastewater.	95
Low cost technology and conventional treatment systems (both aerobic and anaerobic or in combination) can be employed for the secondary biological treatment of equalized and settled tannery wastes.	23
Tannery effluent can also be satisfactorily treated in admixture with sewage in a sewage treatment plant provided the proportion of tannery effluents is not high.	154
Sorption of odorous gases through a granular sorbent like active carbon. Removal of odor bearing dusts by cyclone separators. Masking the odor with objectionable additives.	20
Total	350

The above table show that Tannery effluent/waste can also be satisfactorily treated in admixture with sewage is the maximum used awareness/prevention tool.

Table 9: Impact of tannery waste pollution on female fertility

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Women in tannery area are less fertile than other area.	124	117	23	57	39	3.74	9.52
Women in tannery area have high miscarriage rate than other area.	132	125	25	48	20	3.86	9.82
Women have difficulty to get pregnant at tannery area in BD	129	132	22	36	31	3.83	9.88
Women have complexity at pregnancy in tannery area.	133	135	28	33	21	3.93	10.08
Women have severe sickness in pregnancy period at tannery industry area in BD.	128	134	31	38	19	3.90	9.92

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)
 N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). The highest mean indicates that most of the respondents agreed on that variable. The lowest Standard deviation indicates that there is a stability of ideas on the specific variable. Here the author get highest mean which indicate most of the respondents agreed on the statements. A low standard deviation means there was a lot of agreement about the answers. Here the author get high SD means there was a wide range of answers, indicating disagreement.

Table 10: Impact of tannery waste on Child Development

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Children are comparatively more sick at tannery area in BD.	114	119	42	51	24	3.71	9.19
Children have complex mentality at tannery area in BD.	121	125	37	44	23	3.79	9.49
Children are less meritorious at tannery area in BD.	125	133	34	38	20	3.87	9.81
Children are less physically active at tannery area in BD.	123	128	27	33	39	3.75	9.61
Children are less attentive in study at tannery area in BD.	131	135	32	25	27	3.91	10.01

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)
 N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). A low standard deviation means there was a lot of agreement about the answers. High SD means there was a wide range of answers, indicating disagreement.

Table 11: Impact of tannery waste on Occupation

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tannery industry started dumping waste in the river, so most of the fishermen gradually leave fishing profession.	133	136	31	23	27	3.93	10.10
Most of fishermen became shopkeeper, day labourer, rickshaw pullers and many had to find other jobs.	135	139	28	21	27	3.95	10.26
Tannery waste covered cultivable land, as a result farmers also lost their work.	136	131	34	25	24	3.94	10.05
Tannery waste decrease the fertility of cultivable land, so production of fruits and vegetables are decreased as a results seller of fruits, vegetables are make loss in their business.	131	135	32	28	24	3.92	10.01

Tannery waste killed many rivers in BD, so water transportation system is hampered and many of boatmen lost their job.	118	121	38	35	38	3.70	9.28
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(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)
 N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). A low standard deviation means there was a lot of agreement about the answers. High SD means there was a wide range of answers, indicating disagreement.

Table 12: Impact of tannery waste pollution on land

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Large amount of tannery wastes dump into the rivers as well as land that have made an inhabitable situation for the living people of those areas.	114	117	39	47	33	3.66	9.10
Tannery waste reduce cultivable land on the river bank in BD.	132	136	33	26	23	3.94	10.08
Tannery waste increase river bank side.	123	117	36	35	39	3.71	9.31
Tannery wastes destroy various rivers flow which increase land area.	128	131	32	28	31	3.85	9.81
Tannery discharge wastes to the marshy land like rivers and canals which carry toxic chemical like H ₂ S (water), NH ₃ (ammonia), poisonous chlorine and nitrogen based gases. These waste reduce fertility of land.	137	134	33	24	22	3.97	10.17

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)
 N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). Here the author get high SD which indicate high disagreement among the answers.

Table 13: Impact of tannery waste pollution on social life

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tannery waste hampered road, pavement which causes problem in transportation system, accident etc.	135	139	26	27	23	3.96	10.25
Tannery waste increase unemployment which causes crime such as theft, robbery hijacking, murder etc.	118	131	31	35	35	3.75	9.55
Tannery waste cause diseases of people which enhance mental disturbance, devaluation of morality, ethics.	125	129	34	38	24	3.84	9.68
Tannery waste polluted environment, emit bad smell which causes anger, hot temper, quarrelsomeness nature among public.	136	141	26	25	22	3.98	10.34
Tannery waste sometimes cause miscarriage of women which disturbed family life even social	121	128	36	31	34	3.77	9.54

life.							
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(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)

N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). Here the author get high SD which means high disagreement among the answers.

Table 14: Impact of Tannery waste pollution on financial condition of the respondents

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Rivers are the main source of water for all, But rich people used electricity run pumps, resulting in rise in the monthly expenditure.	124	128	33	37	28	3.81	9.62
Many profession people like fisherman, fruit seller, vegetables sellers, boatmen are leave or lost their work due to tannery waste destroy various rivers.	131	127	35	33	24	3.88	9.79
Diseases are on the rise in the area due to contaminated river water which increases expenditure of the respondents.	127	133	36	29	25	3.88	9.85
Tannery waste management tool increase the expenditure of the people.	137	135	32	26	20	3.98	10.20
Tannery waste hampered road, footpath as a result transportation cost is increased.	134	139	33	22	22	3.97	10.23

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)

N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). High SD means there was a wide range of answers, indicating disagreement.

Table 15: Impact of tannery waste pollution on Social-ecological inequalities' relation to eating behaviour

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tannery waste reduces the fertility of cultivable land as a result fruits and crops are less produced at these area which affect eating behaviour of the people.	133	136	34	25	22	3.95	10.11
Tannery waste hampered fishing, farming and many profession as a result their earning is decreased and the affected people take inexpensive food item.	135	139	28	21	27	3.95	10.26
Tannery waste cause various diseases which affect food culture and eating behaviour of the respondents.	112	116	37	41	44	3.60	9.03
Tannery waste decrease cultivable land size which which can effect the eating behaviour of the respondents.	117	123	33	36	41	3.68	9.32
Tannery waste destroy rivers as a results fish are died and people can't take fish as a meal in this locality.	134	138	32	27	19	3.97	10.20

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)

N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). High SD means there was a wide range of answers, indicating disagreement.

Table 16: Impact of tannery waste pollution on Social-ecological inequalities' relation to physical activity

Statement Scale (5-1)	Strongly Agree	Agreed	No Response	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
Various type of health problems causes due to tannery waste affect physical activity adversely.	137	141	26	21	25	3.98	10.38
Poisonous chemical and other toxic waste products of the tannery industry cause pollution which severely impact on human being that reduce physical activity.	139	143	23	21	24	4.01	10.50
The toxic metals in tannery effluent cause lethal effects, genotoxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity to microorganisms, aquatic organisms, plants, animals, and human beings which reduce physical activity of people.	142	144	25	22	17	4.06	10.63
Chromium salts, phenolics, tannins, organic matter, among others products, are constantly released to the environment in tannery wastewater. These pollutants offer environmental risks to the aquatic life and human health and can severely hampered physical activity.	136	141	23	26	24	3.97	10.35
Biological hazards Raw hides and skins may be contaminated with a variety of bacteria, molds, yeasts, etc., and various diseases (e.g., anthrax, leptospirosis, tetanus, Qfever, brucellosis, etc.) which reduce physical activity of people.	138	143	22	24	23	3.99	10.47

(Strongly agree = 5, Agree = 4, No response = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1)

N=350

The range of interpreting the Likert scale mean score is as follows: 1.0-2.4 (Negative attitude), 2.5-3.4 (Neutral attitude), and 3.5-5.0 (Positive attitude). Here the author get high standard deviation which means high disagreement among the answers.

Table 17: Average Production and Cost of tannery waste affected area

S.No	Crops	Average cost(In BDT)	Average production:
1	Rice	21.90 - 26.80 Tk./kg	43,667 hg per ha
2	Potato	Per hectare total cost of potato was Tk. 2, 69, 873.	13.08 t/ha
3	Wheats	41.50 Tk/Kg	28,990 hg per ha.
4	Vegetables	Per hectare gross cost of production of tomato, cauliflower and cabbage were Tk. 121000, 126977 and 125522, respectively.	2.32 million tonnes.

Table 18: Average Production and Cost of non-affected area

S.No	Crops	Average cost(In BDT)	Average production (In Hector)
1	Rice	14.98 - 21.40 Tk./kg	48,667 hg per ha
2	Potato	Per hectare total cost of potato was Tk. 2, 64, 873	18.08 t/ha.
3	Wheats	36.50 Tk/Kg	32,996 hg per ha.
4	Vegetables	Per hectare gross cost of production of tomato, cauliflower and cabbage were Tk. 118000, 116977 and 120522, respectively .	4.32 million tonnes.

The above two table show that the average production cost is high in tannery waste affected area and average production rate is low in tannery waste affected area than non affected area. Impact of tannery waste pollution on female reproductive system:

Table 19: Situation with menstrual cycle

Situation with menstrual cycle	Number	Percent
Regular	38	26.21
Irregular	107	73.79
total	145	100

Table 19 show that the situation with menstrual cycle where the reproductive health conditions respondents were asked about the state of their menstrual cycle in last one year. 26.21% of respondents had a regular menstrual cycle whereas 73.79% had irregular menstrual cycle in last one year.

Table 20: Situation with menstrual cycle

Situation with menstrual cycle	Yes	No	Total
Menstrual cycle irregularities before living in the tannery area.	29	27	56
Menstrual cycle irregularities after living in the tannery area.	71	18	89
Total	100	45	145

Figure 20 shows the irregular menstrual cycle before living in the tannery among the 29 respondents who had irregular menstrual cycle, were again asked whether they had these irregularities before living in the tannery or not. 52% replied –no and 48% replied –yes i.e. they had irregular menstrual cycle before living in the tannery industry area.

Test of Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship exists between respondent’s awareness and their education level.

Here the author used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) test.

Here the calculated value of r is= -.049494859

So there is a negative correlation exists between respondent’s awareness and their education level. So high education level not indicate high awareness.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship exists between respondent’s health issue and their education level.

Here the author used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) test.

Here the calculated value of r is= 0.645058787

So there is moderate positive correlation exists between respondent’s health issue and their education level. So high education level not indicate low health issues.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between respondent’s awareness and respondent’s health issue.

Here the author used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) test.

Here the calculated value of r is= 0.056442251

So there is weak positive correlation exists between respondent’s awareness and respondent’s health issue. So high respondent’s awareness/preventive measures not indicate low health issues. Which means the awareness policy against tannery waste pollution in Bangladesh is not effective.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant impact of respondent’s awareness on female fertility.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant impact of respondent’s awareness on female fertility.

Here the author used independent t test.

The calculated t value is = 36.98

Here t table value is = 0.00000

If the absolute value of the t-value is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, There is no significant impact of respondent’s awareness on female fertility, is reject or not true.

So the alternative hypothesis, there is a significant impact of respondent’s awareness on female fertility is true.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of respondent’s age on respondent’s health issue.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant impact of respondent’s age on respondent’s health issue.

Here the author used independent t test.

The calculated t value is = 7.98

Here t table value is = 0.00000

If the absolute value of the t-value is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, There is no significant impact of respondent’s age on respondent’s health issue is reject or not true.

So the alternative hypothesis, there is a significant impact of respondent’s age on respondent’s health issue is true. Children and old people are mostly affected by tannery waste pollution in Bangladesh.

Goodness of Fit test:

Null Hypothesis 3: Type of tannery waste pollution have no association with type of health hazard on living being in tannery area in BD.

Alternative Hypothesis: Type of tannery waste pollution have a great association with type of health hazard on living being in tannery area in BD.

Table 21: Observed Value

Type of Health Hazard:	Tannery Waste Impact			Total	Chi-Square Test
Name of Diseases:	Air Pollution	Water Pollution	Soil Pollution		21.98853116
Dizziness, headache, irritation of eyes, skin or lungs, allergic reactions on human.	26	35	37	98	
Adverse pregnancy and fertility outcomes in animals or humans.	21	51	66	138	
Poisoning of liver, kidney of human.	39	50	25	114	
Total	86	136	128	350	

Here the author used Chi-Square test,

The chi square Calculated value= 21.98853116

At 0.05 level of significance and 4 degrees of freedom the Chi-square table value is= 9.49

So Chi square Calculated value >Chi-square table value

If our chi-square calculated value is greater than the chi-square critical value, then we reject our null hypothesis.

So the null hypothesis , Type of tannery waste pollution have no association with type of health hazard on living being in tannery area in BD is rejected and the alternative hypothesis," Type of tannery waste pollution have a great association with type of health hazard on living being in tannery area in BD." is true.

So the impact of tannery waste on air pollution, water pollution, soil pollution are different and these three type of pollution cause different type of diseases on living beings at the tannery industry area in Bangladesh.

Null Hypothesis 4: Tannery waste pollution has no direct association with the reproduction of human beings. (Male & female)

Alternative Hypothesis: Tannery waste pollution has a direct association with the reproduction system of human being (male &female)

Likelihood of developing Reproductive Health related problem / diseases in tannery area based on living year (for female).

Table 22

Duration	Respondents those are suffering from various problem	Respondents those are not suffering from various problem	Total	Pearson Chi square Test
Living more than one year in the tannery industry area.	72	11	83	11.23
Living less than one years in the tannery industry area.	39	23	62	
Total (Female)	111	34	145	

Here the author used Chi Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is= 11.23

Degrees of Freedom=(2-1)*(2-1)=1

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841

So chi square cal>chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is greater than the chi-square critical value, then we reject our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, Tannery waste pollution has no direct association with the reproduction of living beings is reject or not true. So the alternative hypothesis tannery waste pollution has a direct association with the reproduction of females is true.

ODDS Ratio, OR = (72*23)/(39*11) = 3.86

Since OR >1, it is suggesting that the respondents(female) who are living in the tannery industry area for more than one year are 3.86 times likely to develop various reproductive health problem or disease than those who are living in the tannery industry area for less than one year.

Likelihood of developing Reproductive Health related problem/ diseases in tannery area based on living year (for male).

Table 23

Duration of living tannery industry area	Respondents those are suffering from various problem	Respondents those are not suffering from various problem	Total	Chi Square
Living more than one year in the tannery industry area.	91	12	103	2.34
Living less than one years in the tannery industry area.	74	18	92	
Total (male)	165	30	195	

Here the author used Chi Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is = 2.34

Degrees of Freedom = (2-1)*(2-1)=1

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841

So chi square cal < chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is less than the chi-square critical value, then we "fail to reject" our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, Tannery waste pollution has no direct association with the reproduction of male is accepted.

ODDS Ratio, OR = (91*18)/(74*12)= 1.84

Since OR >1, it is suggesting that the respondents(male) who are living in the tannery industry area for more than one year are 1.84 times likely to develop various reproductive health problem or disease than those who are living in the tannery industry area for less than one year.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association exists between reproductive health problem based on the type of exposure to chemicals (For female).

Likelihood of developing of RH problem or disease development based on the type of exposure to chemicals (For female):

Table 24

Level of toxic chemicals:	Respondents those are suffering from various problem	Respondents those are not suffering from various problem	Total	Pearson Chi-square (P-value)
Living in presence of much toxic chemicals.	73	13	86	3.15
Living in presence of less toxic chemicals.	43	16	59	
Total(female)	116	29	145	

Here the author used Chi Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is = 3.15

Degrees of Freedom = (2-1)*(2-1)=1

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841.

So chi square cal < chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is less than the chi-square critical value, then we "fail to reject" our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, there is no significant association exists between reproductive health problem based on the type of exposure to chemicals (For female), is true.

ODDS ratio, OR= (73*16)/(43*13)=2.09

Since OR >1, it is suggesting that the respondents(female) who are living in the presence of much toxic chemicals area are 2.09 times likely to develop various reproductive health problem or disease than those who are living in the presence of less toxic chemicals tannery industry area.

Likelihood of developing of RH problem or disease development based on the type of exposure to chemicals (For male):

Table 25

	Respondents those are suffering from various problem	Workers those are not suffering from various problem	Total	Pearson Chi-square (P-value)
Living in presence of much toxic chemicals.	91	25	116	0.047684298
Living in presence of less toxic chemicals	63	16	79	
Total(male)	154	41	195	

Here the author used Chi Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is= 0.047684298

Degrees of Freedom = (2-1)*(2-1) = 1

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841.

So chi square cal < chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is less than the chi-square critical value, then we "fail to reject" our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, There is no significant association exists between reproductive health problem based on the type of exposure to chemicals (For male) is true.

ODDS ratio, OR= $(91 \cdot 16) / (63 \cdot 25) = 0.92$

An odds ratio less than 1 indicates that the condition or event is less likely to occur in the first group.

Null Hypothesis 04: Level of tannery waste pollution has no direct association with plant life in the tannery industry area.

Table 26

Level of toxic chemicals	Plants are all died	Plants are alive but not in reproductive stage	Total	Chi square Test
Grow in presence of much toxic chemicals	1129	1040	2169	100.17
Grow in presence of less toxic chemicals	978	442	1420	
Total	2107	1482	3589	

Here the author used Chi-Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is= 100.17

Degrees of Freedom= $(2-1) \cdot (2-1) = 1$

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841.

So chi square cal > chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is greater than the chi-square critical value, then we reject our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, Tannery waste pollution has no direct association with plant life in those area is rejected or not true. So the alternative hypothesis, Tannery waste pollution has a direct association with plant life in those areas.

Null Hypothesis: Level of tannery waste pollution has no direct association with poultry health.

Table 27

Level of tannery waste pollution:	Poultry are all sick.	Poultry are alive but not in reproductive stage	Total	Chi Square
Living in presence of much toxic chemicals.	13528	9717	23245	374.57
Living in presence of less toxic chemicals.	10978	11355	22333	
Total	24506	21072	45578	

Here the author used Chi-Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is= 100.17

Degrees of Freedom= $(2-1) \cdot (2-1) = 1$

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841.

So chi square cal > chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is greater than the chi-square critical value, then we reject our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, level of tannery waste pollution has no direct association with poultry health is reject or not true.

Null Hypothesis: Level of tannery waste pollution has no direct association with food chain.

Table 28

Level of tannery waste pollution	Food chain affected	Food chain not affected	Total	Chi square
Living in presence of much toxic chemicals.	121	87	208	0.982545182
Living in presence of less toxic chemicals.	75	67	142	
Total	196	154	350	

Here the author used Chi-Square test,

The calculated Chi- square value is= 0.982545182

Degrees of Freedom= $(2-1) \cdot (2-1) = 1$

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841.

So chi square cal < chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is less than the chi-square critical value, then we "fail to reject" our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, level of tannery waste pollution has no direct association with food chain is true or accepted.

Null Hypothesis 5: Low impact tanning methods has no direct association with lower levels of waste and pollution.

Table 29

Impact of methods	Methods		Total	Chi square
	Vegetable Tanning	Chrome Free Tanning		
Fewer Hazardous Chemicals	109	88	197	0.027179026
Less Water Waste	86	67	153	
Total	195	155	350	

Here the author used Chi-Square test,

The calculated Chi - square value is = 0.027179026

Degrees of Freedom = $(2-1)*(2-1)=1$

At 0.05 level of significance and 1 degrees of freedom the table value of Chi square value is=3.841

So chi square cal < chi square table

If our chi-square calculated value is less than the chi-square critical value, then we "fail to reject" our null hypothesis. So the null hypothesis, low impact tanning methods has no direct association with lower levels of waste and pollution is true.

Discussion & Analysis:

This review of a systematically selected set of researches allows us to draw tentative conclusions and produced a clear picture of the role of social-ecological inequality in tannery waste polluted area in Bangladesh. It is clear that ecological, material and social circumstances relate to people's health-related behaviour.

The researches show that tannery industry area people are mostly illiterate. High educated people are less likely to live this tannery industry area. The livestock mortality rate, pure water problem, movement problem are the major livestock problem in the tannery industry area in Bangladesh. Again in the tannery industry area production cost is high and production rate is low compare to no affected area. The research show that awareness/preventive tool against tannery waste pollution is not very much effective. The high level of respondent's awareness/preventive tool not indicate low health issues.

The research proves that tannery waste pollution has a great impact on female fertility and pregnancy. Women in these tannery industry area experience more miscarriage rate than other area women in Bangladesh. Women are also face adverse pregnancy and low fertility rate in these tannery industry area in Bangladesh.

Here the author also show that tannery waste pollution has an adverse impact on child development, occupation, social life, landed area, financial condition, eating behaviour, physical activity. Tannery industry area children are comparatively less meritorious and active than other area children. In tannery industry area the people's eating culture, occupation are gradually changed. Social life and physical activity of people are destroyed or hampered day by day in these area.

The research show that, in the case of affected livestock sector water pollution and mortality is the highest number of problem. The livestock businessmen make loss. The cattle, cow, goat and poultry affected by various diseases due to tannery waste pollution.

This research show that high educated people have not high level of awareness or not take high level of prevention against tannery waste pollution.

From the research we know that high education level not indicate low health issues. So people of different level of education are catch by disease through tannery waste pollution.

The research show that there is weak positive correlation exists between respondent's awareness and respondent's health issue. So high respondent's awareness/preventive against tannery waste pollution not indicate low health issues. Which means the awareness policy/ prevention measure against tannery waste pollution in Bangladesh is not very much effective.

From this research we know that, there is a significant impact of respondent's awareness on female fertility. So if the women take necessary precaution they can protect from miscarriage, infertility and adverse pregnancy at the tannery industry area in Bangladesh.

The research found that there is a significant impact of respondent's age on respondent's health issue. Children and old people are mostly affected by the tannery waste pollution diseases in Bangladesh.

The author also found that type of tannery waste pollution have a great impact on type of health hazard on living being in tannery area in Bangladesh.

The research also show that tannery waste has a severe impact on plants, poultry health and food chain. In this research the author find that, low impact tanning methods has no direct association with lower levels of waste and pollution in BD.

Nonetheless, the analysis indicated that there was considerable scientific interest in socio - ecological health-related behaviors and health inequality in Bangladesh.

Although tannery industry has huge positive impact on our economy and export income but its adverse impact disturbed greatly the inhabitants of the tannery industry area of BD. India and Pakistan are two neighbour countries of Bangladesh, also faced the adverse impact of tannery affluent. Research showed that, the tannery processes contribute pollution load in the form of solid waste from various processes (Daniels, 2005) in Vellor district Tamil Nadu India. Tannery waste also affect the environment and ecological balance in Pakistan.

Mitigation Measures to Avoid Health & Environmental Hazards:

Regardless of its terrible outcomes, its endowment to the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) in a poor country like Bangladesh is not insignificant. Alternately a viable approach should be taken to lessen the detrimental consequences of tanneries. Following steps may be taken for feasible application:

- Shifting the tanneries outside the main Dhaka and Chattogram cities.
- Establishment of Central Effluent Treatment Plant (CETP) for treating the tannery waste water.
- Assuring the protection of workers by providing gloves, masks, shoes, etc.
- Estimate the effects of tannery wastes on soil quality with concerning to physical biological studies.
- Using of chemicals within allowable limits in consequence with the regulation provided by the Department of Environment (DoE).
- Conducting the operating hours of the tannery industry so that noise pollution does not affect inhabitant of the surrounding area.
- Appropriate disposal of solid wastes containing detrimental chemicals should be ensured, no wastes should be burnt in open place under any situations.
- Tannery wastes used as poultry food ought to be inspect before it is given to the poultry farm, solid waste containing Chromium must not be used as poultry food.
- Taking into account the socioeconomic aspect of Bangladesh low cost coagulant such as alum, lime and ferric chloride can be chosen for the treatment of tannery waste
- Effective Environmental Management Plan (EMP) must be initiated for maximum pollution reduction.

Conclusion:

In Bangladesh the tannery industries distress the soil and river water environment and thus alleviate ecological balance. This research has disclosed that the tanning activities involve significant environmental hazards. Ultimately, it could be said that enough defending measures should be taken in tannery industrial activities consciously to ensuring safe, sound and healthy environment for the greater benefit of Bangladesh. The research shows that respondent' health-related behaviour is related to education, occupations social background. Health education, precaution, awareness should be effective in influencing attitudes among respondent' social-ecological system and health-related issues. After all, the promotion of health factors in tannery industries area provide an unfavourable close co-operation between home and tannery industry offering equality in health and a growing possibility in preventing less fortunate health problems later in life. Lastly, women and children were found to be more vulnerable to social-ecological disparities than men. Therefore, particular attention should be placed on female and child whilst developing and implementing health promotion strategies and policies in these locality.

Future Research & Implication:

From the results of the discussion portion, the writer has suggestions for the application of this study:

- For companies: The author hope that this research can be used as a reference in order to build rapport between living beings and ecology and bring with it many benefits for the human beings.
- For the Academic field: The study can be used for reference for any students that will perform research about social-ecology and social-economic developments.
- For future studies: Any future studies should focus on different and new areas/locations of research such as India and Pakistan so that research and information into the effects of ecology and living beings. Future researcher can also study the impact of textile industry on social-ecological development of Bangladesh and other regions.

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